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Perceptions of Research Supervisors Regarding Postgraduate Students' Self-Regulated Learning, Emotional Intelligence and Possible Stressors to Influence Wellbeing and Research Execution

Saira Khanm

Ph.D. Education Research Scholar, Institute of Education, University of Sargodha, Sargodha

Muhammad Uzair-ul Hassan

Associate Professor, Institute of Education, University of Sargodha, Sargodha

ABSTRACT

Postgraduate research is a challenging endeavor that is closely supervised by expert faculty members who help students become autonomous researchers and integrate them into the academic community. Research supervisors are perceived by the students as sole ray of hope to best utilize their potential and time to successfully execute the research work. The objective of this study is to pin point the issues and perspectives for the success in research work. It was a narrative description of supervisors. Data was collected by conducting open-ended interview protocol in face to face mode from (n=18) faculty members of public universities of Punjab. Participants were accessed using mixed (purposive and random) sampling technique. The perceptions revealed that supervising students' research is the most complex and finest form of teaching and faculty has to leave a long-lasting impact on the students work and shape his wellbeing. Supervisor in his capacity incorporate desired research skills to positively support their research work. Supervisors expect their students to possess generic and acquired skills like autonomy, critical thinking, self-regulation and emotional-intelligence, communication skills, and research skills such as planning, self-monitoring, self-correction and data driving. Universities play a pivotal role in cultivating a proper research culture by ensuring intellectual faculty and positive learning environment with infrastructure and other resources needed to facilitate the active engagement in research. The nature and time duration of research degree demands ongoing development in research technicalities in form of skills, financial support and time management. To execute this creative task role of supervisor, supervisee, and institution is of utmost importance for success in research work with good coping management strategies proposed by the supervisors and in form of facilities and infrastructure to positively influence the work potential of researchers. The study has implications for supervisors, ORIC, QEC, research counselors, practitioners, managers and future researchers. It advances the discussion on importance of self-regulated learning, emotional intelligence, wellbeing and stressors and stress coping strategies in the field of higher education.

Keywords: *Autonomous Researchers, Academic Community, Learning Environment, Coping Management.*

Introduction

Research is an important part of the academic notch of a university and is increasingly recognized as being vital to innovation. It is the most important driving force towards progress and development for society and one of the most important indicators of national development (Eslamipour et al., 2015; Al-Adawi et al., 2016). In all developed and developing countries, students are engaged in research activities either as a part of their undergraduate or

postgraduate prospectus. Research as a part of education helps to learn more, pursue interests and contributes towards the development of problem-solving skills. Students experience towards scientific research is a mandatory component of modern undergraduate and undergraduate (Siraj et al., 2016; Burgoyne et al., 2010; Sreedharan, 2012; Ogunyemi et al., 2005; Green et al., 2010; Hren et al., 2004). According to various studies, various personal and environmental factors lead students to pursue postgraduate degrees (Incikabi et al., 2013; Tarvid, 2014). Their commitment and learning achievement are dominating reasons for enrolling in doctoral programs (Roths et al., 2017). To develop research skills social-learning theory help to develop human behavior, self-regulation is necessary, and it helps people believe in their capacity to influence both their own lives and the world (Sandhu & Zarabi, 2018). At the same time emotional intelligence is seen as a crucial component of achievement and performance (Iqbal & Qureshi, 2021). It helps in emotional persistence of learners as in higher education institutions they are estimated to be more firm and well aware of learning challenges and future needs (Fida & Satti, 2018). Developing the skills of self-regulation and managing emotions while exploiting various coping strategies may lead to improved wellbeing (Khanm & Hassan, 2024). In fact it is the capacity to recognize the differences between emotions and feelings in terms of the influences of both positive and negative emotions on one's thinking and behavior (Iqbal et al., 2021). Post-graduate students need to develop and demonstrate their potential skills in the form of self-regulated learning and emotional intelligence. These skills help the researcher face demanding situations (Khanm & Hassan, 2024).

Based on the principles of educational psychology and learning, these skills should be positively associated with academic success, serving as a crucial tool to prevent academic stress (Howard, J. L., 2021). Elements/ or behaviors are characteristics that make a person happy and improve their general mental health (Seligman et al, 2014). These are the key contributors that work on making people healthier and more effective at what they do instead of just treating mental illness (Cherniss et al, 2006). Contributors involve intelligent use of emotions, self-regulated learning, optimism, resilience, gratitude, hope, self-efficacy, mindfulness, empathy, motivation, curiosity and many more. When it comes to emotional intelligence and self-regulation to perform well in educational institutions, self-efficacy, motivation, and consistent efforts are the most important traits (Cuartero, N., & Tur, 2021). The scientific literature generally supports a moderate correlation between emotional intelligence and self-regulation with academic performance. However, this correlation can be influenced by other positive psychological factors such as self-efficacy belief during research work (Al Omari, et al 2023, McEown, K., et al 2024). These factors contribute to more adaptive behavior. A study by Baños, R., et al (2023) indicated that certain components of emotional intelligence, specifically emotional clarity and healing, had a favorable and direct impact on one's belief in their ability to succeed academically. In addition, the ability to restore emotional well-being was Shengyao et al. found to be a significant predictor of both behavioral and emotional involvement.

There is evidence that emotional intelligence and coping mechanisms of stress affect self-efficacy of learner in significant manner (Morales-Rodriguez & Pérez-Marmol, 2019). In the same manner, the ability to cool down when having emotional distress and ability to change the mood, pushing oneself in comfort zone in face of anxiety is only possible being self-regulated (McClelland M & Geldhof, 2018). There is an elevated threat of mental health and conflicts for those who have lack of self-regulation or unproductive skills. By fostering students' self-regulation an efficient learning environment can be created (De Corte, 2019). In this manner advanced self-regulation is linked with advanced wellbeing, that includes good

balanced health, ability to develop and sustain efficient social relationships, and accommodative execution in home or university (Buckner J.C & Mezzacappa E, 2009). It is a central point of human performance and facilitates the individuals in flourishing quest of individual's goals. To facilitate the learners, provide them autonomy, and meet the day-to-day challenges of this terminal degree, they must be addressed at individual, supervisory, institutional, and academic levels (Khanm & Hassan, 2024). It is a complicated, multifaceted construct that we approach by developing the competencies required to organize and monitor learning, control time, maintain focus, lessen anxiety, put off fulfillment, and persevere in the pursuit of predetermined goals (Schunk, 2013). There is widespread agreement that self-regulation positively impacts scholastic learning, academic accomplishment, and future success. (Schunk & Greene, 2018; De Corte, 2019). Self-management also gets influenced by good emotional and cognitive intelligence. Work potential and stress of students also fluctuate across the age groups (Taylor & Hamdy, 2013; Kellenberg et al., 2017). At the higher education level, more independence is demanded from students, because they want to take charge of their own learning process (Zimmerman, 2000; Dillon & Greene, 2003), while tackling with more "high risk" tasks and responsibilities, specific SRL skills are required that have the capacity to manage one's learning behavior as well as motivation, and emotions in an effective manner (Shnaubert & Herold, 2020). Adult learners, particularly research students, have been observed to experience increased stress during the learning process, necessitating the identification of suitable and long-lasting supporting measures in the form of coping mechanisms (Kellenberg et al., 2017). Emotional intelligence and self-regulation both are crucial in influencing academic motivation and wellbeing (Chinyere, O. T., & Afeez, Y. S, 2022). Individuals that possess strong skills of emotional intelligence and self-regulation have a greater ability to comprehend and control their own emotions, as well as recognize and react to the emotions of others. This capacity enables individuals to sustain an optimistic perspective, efficiently manage stress, and adjust to evolving circumstances and obstacles. For instance, Emotional intelligence can assist a student in identifying emotions of dissatisfaction and employing effective techniques to sustain motivation when encountering challenging situations or academic obstacles (Zhu, S, 2025). Moreover, students that possess emotional intelligence tend to have heightened empathy and proficiency in their communication, so fostering improved relationships with both peers and educators (Chan, B., et al, 2022). Consequently, this leads to enhanced motivation through heightened social support and active involvement within the academic community. This study proposes that self-regulation plays a vital role in the connection between emotional intelligence and psychological well-being and academic accomplishment.

Significance of the study

Highlight gaps between supervisors' perceptions and students' actual needs. It raised the need of informed training programs for supervisors. To promote wellbeing supervision practices are to be aligned with societal needs of researchers. Such practices are to ensure the contribution postgraduate commitment, determination, retention and satisfaction.

Conceptual framework

Methodology

For this qualitative study research supervisors’ (university teachers’) perspectives related to their supervision experience were explored through open-ended interview protocol. Their views were collected through indirect statements to give richness to data as well as gathering rich, deeper, and broader perceptions of teachers on constructs under study and how they influence differently to different scholars, such as self-regulated learning, emotional intelligence and wellbeing with mediating role of stress coping strategies (N/18) teaching in various public universities of Punjab in different departments. Participants were selected using the purposive sampling technique as they may have more than 5 years university teaching experience as well as approved HEC supervisors. The researcher observed the saturation point after interviewing 18 participants, although four interviews that were conducted for pilot testing were not included in analysis as changes were made in response to these initial interviews. Majority of the respondents were male (11 males and 7 females); only three participants were working as lecturers with 5, 6 and 12-years teaching experience, 8 respondents were Assistant Professors and their experience of university job ranged from 10-17 years, 6 associate professors with 15-18 years teaching experience and a professor who has 18 years’ experience with this university as well as 8 years with another public university of Punjab. Number of years of research supervision ranges for lecturers was 3-7 years, in case of assistant professors’ number of year’s ranges from 10-17 years, experience of research supervision of associate professors ranges from 15-18 years and experience of professor (participant) was 24 years. Research students lecturers supervised were only M. Phil and their numbers were 22, 7 and 5 students respectively. Research students of M. Phil supervised by assistant professors were as in numbers 30,22,20,20,20,18,18 and 15 and PhDs were ranges from 5-1. Numbers of M. Phil students supervised by associate professors were ranged from 50, 45,38,37,33 and 32 and PhDs students supervised were ranged from 5-2. Number of students supervised by Professor participant was 40 M. Phil and 5 PhDs. Significant number of disciplines and Fields of education were explored and finally categorized as Pure and Natural sciences, Social sciences, Art and Humanities and Computer and Information Sciences .6 faculty members were interviewed from pure/Natural sciences,4 from Social sciences,3 from Art and Humanities and 5 from Computer and Information sciences. The results of the interviews were analyzed through -thematic analysis. Codes used helped h to explore the key themes and sub-themes most frequently used by participants and to view source data by areas of coding similarities.

Results and Discussion

Table 1

In this table all the concepts, themes, constructs related indicators, beliefs of the research supervisors about the variables of the study are highlighted very precisely.

Constructs	Indicators	Subthemes/categories/codes
Self-Regulated Learning as Researchers' skill	Independent learner Practical Learning Teacher as motivational force Step by step /Systematic approach Specific skills	Researcher a self-regulated mature individual Dedication, Dynamic learner, Observer Punctual, Concerned, Interest Critical thinking, Creativity, Individual Differences, Mentorship
Emotional intelligence	Reflecting/writing/technical SMART	Patience, Curiosity, Committed Persistence, Consciousness Seriousness
Wellbeing	Post-graduation students and wellbeing Pre-requisites	To Contribute, Be progressive, Collaboration, Self-management, Research work a team-effort, Proactive effort and interest, Personal Sources a source of SRL, Procrastination pays off Level of Stress and anxiety of researcher, Postgraduate level a level of dignity, For promotion for better earning
Stressors	Issues of researchers/stressors Coping Mechanism offered by the research supervisors. Self-developed Issues of researchers Lack of self-regulation and emotional intelligence an issue	Time/finance/sources/resources management, Inefficacy belief Personal issues Gender issues (female) Societal issues Process related issues Marriage during research phase, Lack Of Coverage/ Publication/ Implementation
Stress scoping strategies		Counseling center to manage stress. Time is best healer/Rational approach. Enhance interaction and connection to be in the right direction. Reassuring-- a conflict management strategy, Maturity of researcher matters. Lessons learnt during research work are long lasting.

Research Objective

To explore the perceptions of research supervisors regarding postgraduate students' self-regulated learning and emotional intelligence during research work, stressors and stress coping strategies and effect of all these on their wellbeing.

Research work and Researcher's Skills

Postgraduate is the phase of development and utilization of technical and intelligent skills, especially self-regulated learning skill and emotional intelligence especially in research context. Self-regulated learning skill enables the students to perform this independent task with more autonomy and confidence and emotional-intelligence provide the students to get motivation and social-skills while interacting with environment and persons and help to develop intrapersonal and interpersonal relationship skills. Such views shared by a teacher that how they put conscious focus on skill development that helps them in research work and later as well:-

"I actually want to develop skills, research skills, the capacity to generate idea, so that they can develop a new thing from existing knowledge, existing material, involving new material with collaboration as the main intention behind this skill acquisition is that so they can think and develop a new thing and take initiative, able to write, generate and link idea from available sources and can link it to literature, what we are doing and what we want to do. According to their abilities I manage and take them as nature has created everyone differently, and as nature has created differently, I manage and perceive them differently and deal with and assign them work as per their capacity and capability. Man is dynamic being, there are variety of people, in the same way capabilities and skills are also different, every research scholar has few qualities, but it depends which ability is more or less, so we deal them accordingly".(skill development).

Most of the respondents have the view that this is the phase of independent learning, exploring an idea and giving shape to ideas, what matters a lot is the attitude of researcher. Most of the times teachers interact such researchers who are goal-oriented, time conscious, they take initiative independently, although individual differences matter a lot in this productive activity. There are few indicators that reflect intelligent skills but at postgraduate level most researchers are in job and their responsibilities are more than their capacity that curtail them to utilize their skills of SRL and EI at utmost level. SRL means according to them: -

"Giving maximum quality time, having interest, having the spirit to explore new ideas/areas novelty, availability of sources and resources, Individual differences scientific attitude, put effort in topic selection, identify the genuine research problem, seriousness, dedication, provide vital reflection, good work, committed behavior and to be much concerned" (Independent Learning).

In experimental subjects, research teachers are much proactive and before relying on researcher's skills they assess their own expertise so that the research work may be workable and reasonable contribution as a teacher shared his perspective: -

"Research work demands innovation and contribution otherwise no use of it, and we provide them material and help them in downloading the material so that the students can students get awareness regarding topic and its whereabouts if we want to get done a genuine work then definitely effort has to put both supervisor and researcher".(Teacher a Motivational/self-regulated Force)

Few respondents shared a stance of highly self-regulated and emotionally intelligent researcher in these words: -

"Some students show serious concern that they do and perform more than our expectation, but few show a very non-serious attitude. As you know research is an attitude and some students

are not as serious as they should be about the completion of work. Behavioral differences are here, commitment and determination is different. The difference can be observed in this way that few students of same session are at completion phases, and few have not yet started.”(Individual differences)

“It depends on individual differences, a student is fond of research work, he did timely and proactively his assigned work, give his full potential and show his interest, but in another case he just want to get degree, and allowance on the basis of it and behaved opposite to the first stance, at PhD level we closely interact and associate each other. Anyhow students get mold with passage of time and seek skills that are acute need of this level”. (Individual Differences)

To know more about their supervisee, their level of research interest and area of interest, their existing level of self-regulation and emotional intelligence research supervisor adopt different method of assessment. In case of subject mostly from art and humanities research skills are not as much established nor they want to establish as identified the reason by few respondents: -

“As much motivation is concerned, we can say out of 20 students 4, 5 are highly motivated, they do good work, and others have only intention to complete degree and get a job and those who are already in job they want to get allowance or increment”.{lack of wellbeing}

Perspective regarding SRLS

The skills, research skills are in both forms, technical skills and intelligent skill researchers possess or should possess were asked in an indirect manner from participants of the study. Researchers collect all those key words that reflect and come into the parameter of self-regulated learning and emotional intelligence to ultimately positively help to influence their wellbeing. These are constructs that can support the variable in an abstract manner. Following perspectives of teachers refer towards the key words that reflect their self-regulated learning skill: -

“Dedication, personal interest observation must be strong. There is a big difference among student and researcher just as poet and layman, as the poet brings forth those elements about which we don’t bother in the same way researcher must have keen and deep observation skill, be sensitive towards research process and problem (Dynamic learner).

“My experience in this respect has been very good, and the reason is that we remain in mentorship of our senior teachers and guide our students step by step. To determine direction or mold it or make it workable we discuss with our teachers as well. To do a positive and new work we discuss with our seniors’ teachers as well”. (Mentorship)

“Serious concern is direly needed, researcher must have critical approach towards his work, he needs to be vigilant, he must critically analyze his work. There are issues (deficiencies) in our work. If a researcher does not have serious concern his critical approach can’t be developed. Surely M.Phil and PhD students work seriously as compared to BS or MSc students” (Critical thinking)

“One thing is that as it is a research work and research mean creativity, investigation, and critical analysis, so it requires aptitude, in research we must analyze the things critically, in our context the teaching pattern adopted in our institutions is thoroughly based on cramming, where the thinking capacity of students is not nourished. (Creativity)

“Yes, sure science student is more problem oriented, and he tried at his level to solve the issues and manage the situation. He plans in such a manner that all those resources that he can get access through his sources avail them for example researchers who are schoolteachers, they use their workplace labs They are much efficient in this sense to use chemicals to facilitate themselves”. (Self-management and problem solving)

Postgraduate students are self-regulated and mature individuals who have the capacity to prepare their complete roadmap: -

"Students at this level are much self-regulated they prepare whole plan, which includes checklist as well, what they have? What did they need? We refer them to other labs through our sources. I think they are mature enough and emotionally intelligent enough how and when and where from to collaborate".

Research work or thesis writing demands from researcher a strong determination and commitment with own self. This is a panic task and is done with serious commitment and consistent effort as shared by a respondent: -

"Those who are committed, they have serious tension and concerned about time and finances they excel well they remain successive and those who take it as relax they suffer financially and consider it will be submitted towards the last in respect of time as well, they take extra semester, repeats experiments as well automatically suffer financially"

Perspective regarding EI

The effect of emotional intelligence was explored along with self -regulated learning skill. Researcher utilizing his own analytical skills develops a distinction between both skills and especially in research context how these skills are used and further improved during this phase. A respondent in detail shared the researchers' state of work in these words: -

"Writing skills of the researcher must develop at M.Phil and PhD level. Whatever they write from a research perspective and research point of view, thinking ability is very much necessary. Taking in view a research article how and at what angle ,how much his mind is working , how much he can think, beside search ability , how he searches literature, how he utilizes data basis websites, how he use social media, as you know this is an era of information technology, there are various new data basis available ,many sources are available online ,there are digital libraries, but until research get access to his relevant and required literature I don't think so that he can get clarity relevant to his topic. All the skills related to searching, computer skills, information technology skills, composing skills data basis, citations management, for data analysis SPSS, NVivo, not only use of these software at basic level but at advance level especially for PhD students it is much necessary, moreover the skill of presentation how to present research work and focus on required articles publishing with thesis submission so that he does not face any delay in research progress and execution. These are few skills that researcher must possess" (Reflecting/Writing and Technical skills).

Beside the reflecting ability that get support through emotional intelligent students EI also facilitate the researcher in research work while executing the creative work and fulfilling other research technicalities. Research work is not a daydream or a standing plan. It is a work that has a long process and procedures and during this journey researcher may have to face lots of hurdles to manage all situational conflicts and to motivate himself time and again he must acquire many social skills that create his capacity for this long and exhausting work.

"Research is a thing that requires a lot of patience but to do work with patience, put effort and show passion to take output. It seems a trend to complete the work speedily." (Patience)

SMART means both self-regulated and emotionally intelligent researcher: -

"Researcher must be SMART enough, they must know how and why they are doing that topic selection, create synopsis."

"They need to be curious. They must possess written skills, must focus on genuine work, they should accept the challenge, to be committed for their work, and if you don't possess writing skill researcher face hard times when he is unable to write what he feels. Another crucial skill

they must possess is presentation writing expression skill which is although not created at M.Phil. phases.” (Curiosity)

Some students got worried, but some didn't even bother. Individual differences are very much prominent at this phase, and they have specific role as one student has completed the work and other has not yet started.

“Few students are very much active ,at this PG level every student is 100% different from the other one ambition of students vary from person to person, few behave like this we simply guide them and they really done it but few of them because of their background, social difference they face few limitations, so we keep open for this to seek help where from they want to seek, as all are ultimately our students, there is issue in this help seeking, students have their own mind set they think this particular teacher can guide me in this particular subject or case so they go, we have taught them in course work, we have interaction with them at course work phase.”(Degree level differences)

Coping Mechanism Offered by the Research Supervisors

Financial issues are addressed by the research supervisors through different strategies and arrangements are made at department level and in few cases at personal level: -

“If he has financial issues we have developed a committee that address and resolve such genuine issues, if we have amount of a project we support them, and if there is time issue we settle it and if personal issues we solve them accordingly. Females have more and different issues as married life issues, kids suffer because of mothers' extra activities and engagements.

Issues of researcher are greater than his other academic neither phase, so nor the researcher before time can plan a coping mechanism until he faced it. At upcoming stage and as time a move on his level of stress is also settled down as he understands that all stages are temporary:-

“A teacher cannot propose or make a material formula, it depends we try only to suggest them in such a way to resolve the matter or issue where we can use any reference or relation (job related issue) in the same manner domestic issues teacher can give suggestion just for goodwill as per his experience, I mostly advise my students to be patient when there is a distressed situation, wait for Allah will guide us and enlighten our path, secondly don't be egoistic, act according to situation.”(Time is best Healer)

Enhanced interaction and connection to be on right direction can be a solution of confronted problems. As practice makes a man perfect, in the same manner focusing on deficient skill and blur area can proved to be a coping strategy: -

Researcher is just like a swimmer as no one can be a swimmer unless he entered the water (rider, driver) in the same way researcher can't be a good content writer unless he practiced writing, make it habit to read in which situation you are, make it a routine, there is lack of fixed routine (SRL) timetable manage, plan, and set goal etc.

Counseling center to manage stress can be a practical solution in such case of researchers' a teacher shared its role and significance: -

“There is trend to hire psychiatrist to manage students stress level, researcher is anyhow in more stress we also have faced this phase, so every degree has a pressure, then those who manage daily works they have low stress level but those who make their work pending they have high stress when they are undone at deadline phase.

Reassuring proved as a conflict management strategy. Researchers' issues are so personal in nature that she was hesitant to disclose her issues in front of me. Although issues are most of the time is genuine and multiple that they are not manageable. The researcher in such situation can slightly think to quit if not managed and addressed in positive manner: -

My focus is how I can take him out of this situation, facilitate him in a manner that he becomes confident, and realize that it is a temporary state and a part of life. I would like to share an example she said "I have lots of issues during this phase I faced and definitely nature of issues was so personal that they I can't share them with you but the only true thing you did for me is that you ever encourage me, motivate me in such a positive manner that it seems to me it will be done, I manage to come, frankly speaking if I were in another's supervisee I quit a long before, I did M.Phil just because of you otherwise I quit it a long ago".

Another teacher shared her point of view that teachers consoling and motivating words can be solid source to boost up from setbacks: -

"It is the duty of supervisor to identify the emotional state of mind of researcher, take them as human beings first console them, satisfy them and next step is to move on work it is easy for me".

Maturity in academic life and overall maturity help the researcher to be more proactive and works as coping strategy: -

"In case of PhD students, they are mature they have problem solving strategies, they can manage well, let them decide, but I told them time and again, you are late, why you are not focusing and doing, your work will get pending and delayed, you must take your work seriously". (Maturity as problem-solving strategy)

Having such tendency to seek support to cope situation and resolving conflicts when researcher develop the capacity to seek help from different sources, it is a significant coping strategy in stressful situation: -

"Seek support from within department, or out of university we encourage them but one thing I recommend any material you get from any source discuss with me one time to check its relevance but overall free option it is to seek help related to their work wherefrom they get". (Personal Sources a coping strategy)

Research work without doubt is a team-effort and this work becomes as much smooth as the research build a team and take relevant help from relevant persons. He is the view: -

"Researcher must invest lot of time, to think, suggest them to take help from other faculty members, students take help from them, moreover we believe on teamwork and for research technical techniques we have a team or group of members we work with them. In whole world integrated research is in trend, even different disciplines are linked through research and researchers who are progressing in same manner".

Researcher and supervisor-oriented scenario to interact and collaborate for proper daily check and balance and keep updated, proper workplace in form research labs, well equipped labs as it is common lacking everywhere. (Interaction)

Post-graduation Students and Wellbeing

Wellbeing of postgraduate students is highly dependent upon the beneficial environmental facilities that help to manage the expectations of this specific population. This phase in fact shapes the wellbeing of researchers not for executing this short, termed work but also for future milestones. As pointed out in a deeper manner by research supervisor: -

"According to my point he is not doing research work for a temporary cause. Usually they do M.Phil or PhD to get advantage (increment), social objectives and other concerns are also here but this ratio is 50%.50% focusing these aspects, but there is acute need of their brain storming that you will get and earn money at a stage but surely money career these short term needs will be fulfilled through this degree but do something that your work and you become honor of society, give your personality a good reflection for society, you become expert at your own point ,you get financial advantage as well as wherever you deliver expose yourself. Look a PhD, M.Phil

scholar is at job somewhere, performing somewhere, you can explore new things and get better through your research, and you will get satisfaction that you are contributing, a feeling of pride. Where you are delivering your delivery will be improved, when we guide our students in these grounds' improvement occur, scholars improve and try to improve".

Wellbeing of researcher especially when he is in executing phase of research thesis highly based on few requisites that flourish his work and develop his perception for this work as shared by a teacher in an effective manner: -

"Researchers must possess these 2,3 requisites, in our context researcher does not even possess that 1 good reading habit good background knowledge, and can justify previous degree and on the basis of that he did M.Phil. or PhD he justified it if he has deeper knowledge at philosophical level, in our context student get a research degree that is degree of philosophy but they don't know philosophy of their discipline, very few have this knowledge and issue is poor reading habit, in the same way they seek short cuts in research work, so that they secure their degree, indulgence is lacking they lack indulgence in topic or area of research". (Requisites)

Experiences a researcher goes through during research phase are not for that particular time and activity but have impact on later stage in personality and development of life style and wellbeing: -

"There are many stances where they manage their official responsibilities, their domestic matters and having other life activities they meet all responsibilities. Fact is although PhD itself is not a short, phased activity. Topic to Conclusion from Chapter 1-5 we complete it but it taught us management skills for whole life, this management PhD taught us, how to manage the things, there are many other factors as well, a very crucial need of today is time management, how you have to timely manage your PhD it is very compulsory, how to balance your responsibilities, and these skills definitely research phase taught us, I have heard a proverb "PhD get you weep and it's a proven fact".

Teacher put a lot of effort for his researcher so that their work gets polished and attained a standard and for this teacher does not rely on his own university sources and resources and even use reference to collaborate: -

"We collaborate with other universities and faculties of science disciplines if their labs are good use that lab, we avail them access and solve their problems".

"We collaborate with them, in this way student's mindset also upgraded and research work also gets polished and refined" (Collaboration)

Postgraduate level a level of dignity is reflected through the researcher's behavior and ambition they show while doing their work. They feel honor while doing this work: -

"Gradually we are moving towards quality work, improved work, they have lab work, they do it with interest at this time as well in our; labs my students are working, interest has developed, they even focus their research future implication, they think we have to perform this work it is beneficial for us".

The degree can have many intentions and promotion, or better earning is one of the reasons for which students pursue this degree: -

"If they want to get promotion after attaining this degree purpose is here, it is separate debate for which purpose they are getting it to acquire more knowledge or to earn, in both cases it is purposeful for them, in my opinion mostly students get ambitious coming to this level, they are professional, they want to earn more they want to excel in career or want to join university anyhow purposeful it is for them."

Genuine work is an enjoyable and happy experience for both research scholar and supervisor. This intention provides them the opportunity to reflect their own self as well as to add in:-

"They enjoy their research work, research journey when topic is of their choice and they are doing genuine research they are excited, they understand their work and feel that they are doing a good work".

When students have done or are at completion phase, they realize that they work not for earning not only to excel in career it is also helping to develop ourselves. Being human and personality development as well a teacher shares the situation of researcher of his department: Research work mostly depend upon good relationship with their supervisor and if research teacher is a convenient person, then not only the work quality may be improved but the confidence level that positively affect their wellbeing is also improved: -

"Positive relationship of supervisee and supervisors, they think in same direction, they understand each other's points easily, relationship is needed to understand the state of mind of supervisee, if he is worried listen to him, facilitate them high tech lab, scholar room peace of mind to regularize supervisor-supervisee relationship for collaboration. Supervisors' availability should be ensured."(Emotional intelligence)

When researcher possesses what is to be needed for this work, it may positively influence his wellbeing and over all research execution: -

"He must have access towards resources proper training should provide to researchers, proper place for researchers, research technicalities awareness courses Mendeley, PSS endnote should be in practice so that the researcher remains updated. So that when they came to university they attend such courses on regular basis, there should be few sections in library, guidelines regarding references etc. must be provided to researchers."(Research technicalities)

Work environment and especially research work demands an environment. As environment is a source of research tendency. In this regard teachers have the opinion that how it is possible: -

"There should be at least one researcher discussion room where they have all facilities, just like that initiative taken by HEC for indigenous scholars to facilitate them with PC and furniture as much they will be facilitated they will work joyfully and in peaceful environment, in my observation up till now progress of that supervisor is going well who has place and space in his office for researchers to sit and to do work. But there must be a collective place for researchers that are not available." (Provision of facilities an indicator of wellbeing)

Post-graduation level is in fact an opportunity for researcher to utilize his previous learning skills in productive and practical manner. As teachers expects from their scholars such: -

"Here must be a utility of knowledge and skills acquired at graduation level must be utilized for their own development and practical knowledge.no need to say first learn then earn acquire the skills then you have broader opportunities. Only label of degree can't guarantee you for better tomorrow skills must be here".

There can be few measures for wellbeing of researcher. Teachers feel the dilemma of researchers on genuine ground, and they suppose that these few steps should be taken for welfare of researcher, and it will work: -

"Research material and proper equipment must be timely available. If not so we are dependent must forward request to someone else, we must pay, wait and we are in handicapped state. Secondly there is no scheme of scholarship PhD indigenous is quite obvious that a PhD student who is above 30,he did job to support himself, but if 30-40 thousand steepened is attached with his research work ,he will remain in lab in university and give maximum time in acquiring research skills as well as completion of his work .He will not opt the position in a private college or 7 scale job. He will work and earn at same place. When we will attach a stipend, we can bind them to stay from 9-5 for the sake of work, research lab work".

Time is money, and it is very much true in case of researcher, as being passive this proactive work cannot be executed and secondly if researcher realizes that their time is precious, in same manner their supervisor will deal them.

HEC projects are a source of funding and financial support for researcher and research supervisor, and it can support the researcher to cope the research expenditures: -

"When researcher got paid work they did it devotedly, they get regular payments, if a researcher is getting monthly Lum sum and his research work is also getting done availing all the chemicals ,labs, equipment, travel free and in this way when they are not in any financial pressure their motivation increased, he also become bound for work, he also give his best considering the matter that he is availing regular income, degree will also got completion at the same time, and he attained research degree without spending a penny on experiment as we as he got the status of consultant".

Research supervisors shared their perspectives on self-regulated learning that it is the ability, a skill and a research skill as well, that researcher must possess and even they are of the opinion that they consciously foster these skills among researchers during research phase. The most prominent themes that refer their self-regulated learning skill are dedication, dynamic learner, observation, punctuality, keen and concerned and interest, critical thinking, creativity, individual differences, mentorship and also help to develop Independent learner, practical learning, motivation and systematic approach.

Research Question: Exploring the Stressors of Post graduate students/researchers.

Research work of a researcher is affected due to various potential stressors. Few are contextual that are very much dominating and even influence the wellbeing of researcher, and few are pre-determined and part and parcel of this degree. Researcher has pointed out the stress factors and discussed in precise manner in qualitative analysis as contribution: -

Issues of Researchers/Stressors

Explored Stressors

Research supervisors share that stress is a predetermined fact for students. Most dominating stressors according to them are self-developed issues of researchers, lack of self-regulation and emotional conflicts and time/finance/sources/resources management, inefficacy belief, personal issues, gender issues (female), societal issues, process related issues, marriage during research phase, lack of coverage/ publication/ implementation.

Stress coping strategies were also suggested by the research supervisors. Stress coping strategies work for better utilizing the skills of self-regulation and emotional intelligence of the post graduate students. Stressors damage the smooth work flow of the researchers for better utility and productivity. Counseling center are needed to manage stress, time is best healer/rational approach, Enhancing interaction and connection to be in the right direction, reassuring as a conflict management strategy, maturity of researcher is conflict resolution, lessons learnt during research work are long lasting so be emotionally strong and be more self-regulated.

Supervisors also make a comparison in a compatible manner what was the situations and practices of HEC years before, the areas that have been channelized and appraised on regular basis also provide the researcher an opportunity to add their additional suggestion they generally discuss during a formal interview. Almost every response has few additional details, reason is that nature of research focus varies from department to department and during the process of collecting and merging themes it came to surface that nature of department is practical(experimental) and theoretical(informational), so the priority in respect of research skills, stressors and stress coping strategies may also vary. Moreover, teachers tried to explain

and align their responses through practical examples, which were their experiences in fact they have gone through as reflected in given words:-

“Research work demands from researcher to have good critical thinking, sound subject knowledge and in respect of research work sound knowledge of research methodologies, data retrieval publishing formatting) It means research formalities require updated knowledge of research software and trends in research so the University must put its emphasis to put into practice research courses, training and e-library setups that not only provide researcher opportunity to keep aligned his research work but to acquire those knowledge and skills that can support him when he became part of academia and share that knowledge to his students, moreover this degree for any individual should not only be the source of getting any financial support, but also development and expression of growth mind-set and consider this post-graduation phase a phase of higher and advance learning”.

They put emphasis on the need of financial support to be provided to research students in form of monthly stipend. This support may ensure their maximum stay at university and consuming maximum time in lab works that may ensure their focus and good quality work, when researcher is free from financial worries, free from other travel fatigue and fully and finally managing his research work or any other assignment assigned but living in same productive environment it

Time/finance/Sources/Resources Management

Research degree because of its long duration demands from researcher to manage the research work with all other day to day activities. Researchers want to be independent financially as early as possible. Students of Public universities faced the challenge of excessive number of students with minimum resource availability. All these situations required strong management.

“There are lots of issues, general and financial specially, researchers must do private job as well with M.Phil or PhD, they can't give their best and full focus to their research work. To financially support themselves someone must join tuition academy or a college, there are research related facilities issues, sometimes lack of chemicals or non-availability of chemicals; they must face such resources issues.”

“In our regional context as per students' socio-economic status is lower middle class, so issues are genuine, they have travelling issues, domestic engagements, research responsibilities, if married then these as well so to manage all these aspects they discuss their personal issues, they discuss research relevant as well about poor writing dilemmas”.

There is huge difference of a graduate student and postgraduate researcher approach. Although the skills developed at previous academic journey may support him in smooth progress and completion, but if there is gap in students' academic potential, it becomes more prominent at this stage, as shared by a respondent in this way: -

“There is no assessment method that offer to facilitate critical point of view, while this approach is snubbed, there is a conventional approach, we discourage questioning and consider it a disturbance, not to ask questions, we trained the students in same way, other thing is that most of the post graduate students are teaching or working somewhere so they focus on work completion not on up gradation. Most of the students have not thought provoking capacity when they come in research phase the issue they face is that they have to evaluate after reading a huge material, they have to analyze, they lack practice of these aspects although the things they have studied in research methodologies and repeatedly told them still they lack the capacity to derive and develop a question after reading material, they don't have this aptitude what to derive ,it's really matter so we as supervisor try to and told them, guide them, obviously focusing on these areas we do something and conclude something”.(Lack of critical approach)

Research work is not a formal phase of academic life. Researcher is not time bound to attend the university and fulfill this task in formal classroom setting. This task may be accomplished at home. What matters a lot is family environment and priorities of family members. What they expect from him and what is need of this degree all matter a lot. Personal issues in few cases become so prominent that they take shape of a stressor that hamper his way forward. As a teacher is of the opinion: -

“Personal issues are also related to finance, they share that if he did not do a job he will suffer, marriage issues, married life issues, so they can’t fully concentrate on their research work, and it suffer automatically”. (Personal issues)

In formal classroom setting at any level gender differences are always obvious but become more prominent when research process starts and, in many cases, a new phase of life take start and how the researcher with many other roles manage this: -

“Our social set up is such that females have issues ,there is a communication series among supervisor and supervisee (emotionally Intelligence) required as it’s a adult phase and scholar is not a child and they have social responsibilities so issues are here and we both during research work got attached got affiliated being human being we take care of each other ,we have to spend a long time so kith and kin all type of circumstances we face they face, and I don’t take it a relationship of supervisor and supervisee this is a relationship a bonding of two human beings. Majority of PhD students are married in age mostly above 30 so the life matters, family matters, job matters, domestic issues so they considering us mature in age and experience discuss their issues with us”.(gender issues)

Lack of facilities become major stressor for researcher when they have not such family conditions that can facilitate them and in the same manner university environment is not conducive for researcher. In our social set up major source of stress and anxiety are shared by a respondent: -

“Many issues are within our society that pressurize the students, it can be their domestic life, professional life, or educational stress when they want to do and understand the things(research)then we try to compensate them try to console them, encourage them, share our personal experiences to motivate them, we did so to uplift their morale, consider this an aspect and part of this phase, this is routine ,normal, don’t go on setbacks don’t quit but to move and progress the common things we do”.(societal issues)

Continue this research degree without personal earning source is a major stress factor for researcher, but those who are having job they face job place additional stressor and even management issues as well as shared: -

“Mostly PhD students are employs as well so mostly they have job related issues. At job place they have leave sanctioning issue, senior junior, boss, cooperation, they discuss, some researchers have travelling issue. I don’t think that they have any concern regarding research work, I think they put effort the things are available, otherwise we show them path how to search material.”(work-place issues)

Research work demands technical skills from researcher, when they have any insufficient knowledge and skills that can support them in this potential work; it is a source of anxiety for them.

“Main issue is method related how to perform the assigned work, how to select topic and search relevant literature, how to confine and refine it, when viva will be arranged”(research methodologies)

Another stress factor that is peculiar to these postgraduate students is their marriages. Marriage at this phase is frequently practiced. In case researcher got married what type of future issues they can have, that can not only damage their workflow but also demotivate them when their tasks are diversified: -

"In case of female scholars their research work is going on and they got married, then suddenly a new experience with new gender, new living set up, new people new environment and to manage research work, they have lot of issues they face, immaturity, no experience and they get disappointed, get worried and in few cases they even express that are ready to quit at this point supervisor has to perform the role of a civilized person".(Marriage during Research Phase)

When it is assumed that a researcher is an individual who possess self-regulated learning skill and he is emotionally intelligent person, and these characteristics support him in his research work as well as positively flourish his wellbeing. When a researcher faces any difficulty or lack of ability to support his work, it ultimately damages his self-perception. He becomes under confident and thinks this task that is not in his command:-

"When a person is not satisfied with his work, his workflow in not proper, he is having chemical issue, labs issues, he feels disappointed and feel stress and a good supervisor will be that who will try to solve the problems of scholars, avail them access from other universities, encourage, motivate and assure them that I am with you to solve the issue". (Inefficacy Belief)

A student is working progressively or not he has the capacity to do his work. In such situations when researcher is not giving required time and energy to his work he suffered and to satisfy his supervisor he puts forward lame excuses that the teacher intelligently got familiar. To meet such situation, he usually did: -

"I think those students who don't want to do work they share their problems that my job issue, my family issue, my laptop got stuck, I am not getting this material, that material, in fact they are not capable enough to understand their work and they blame these things".(Procrastination)

Lack of self-regulation and emotional-intelligence becomes an issue for researcher and the status of researcher becomes like that: -

"Inability of research mind set, research skills are not taught at previous level. Students are not curious, so they stuck. They don't know about standardized sources, on which area to focus, what to derive and draw from that article".

Postgraduate researcher must put a lot of effort in research creativity, and he is doing all this not for a short period of time. He expects from this work future implementation and if the situation is not taking that shape, it may damage his wellbeing as: -

"First thing is to consider where we can implement it, a lot of coverage is not given coverage to our research work in our country ,they are not as much goal oriented or think this in long run that they pursue for publication, research planning demands further how to implement this research, promote , give time students don't go on publication but they consider that completion is the only achievement, incremented they have gained because of government job and it's enough that thesis has submitted and ok enough responsibility over." (Lack of Coverage)

Conclusion

Roles and responsibilities of research supervisor are dynamic but still there is huge space on his part to foster the skills of self-regulated learning and emotional intelligence that help to manage the stressors and provide a smooth coping mechanism to excel the research scholar in academic activities as well as prepare for bright and progressive future. The analysis revealed that the postgraduate students are emotionally intelligent as their understanding and utility of

the construct was inquired through indirect questions but research supervisors in detail share their perspective how they use emotional intelligence as a skill when they interact the different persons and places during research work and manage the conflicts in smart manner that are common to researchers' journey. The findings bring out important themes that indicate their emotional intelligence include reflecting, writing and technical skills, patience, SMART, curiosity, committed, persistence, consciousness and seriousness according to the research supervisors.

The perspective shared by the majority of the research supervisors that students are progressive and positive towards their research work as well as towards their degree execution, that reflect their wellbeing. The indicators of wellbeing are prominent through the significant repetition of the positive themes like to contribute, be progressive, collaboration, self-management, research work a team-effort, proactive effort and interest, personal sources a source of SRL, procrastination pays off, level of stress and anxiety of researcher, postgraduate level a level of dignity, and for promotion for better earning. These key themes were true indicators of their wellbeing according to the research supervisors.

This study set a stage for further investigation into the effectiveness of self-regulated learning, emotional intelligence, wellbeing and practicing stress coping strategies through training of research supervisors to better understand and upgrade the wellbeing of their students as the future of an individual is associated with the nourishment and utility of these skills. At postgraduate level students are mature and conscious enough to plan the future as their happiness, hopes and energies are associated with accomplishment of their postgraduate level. Students' skills need to be facilitated in the best positive way. Emphasis on fostering all these skills through pedagogical practices is direly needed. For research skill improvement conferences, workshops, symposiums should be conducted on regular basis to align academic research activities for wellbeing and motivation.

An environment that flourish an individual student and facilitate him such environmental and technical support needed to be addressed by the university administration to boost the morale of this particular group of elite learners. Through maximizing the role and responsibilities of ORICs by fulfilling the needs of researchers in form of skills, clusters and opportunities to make research a top priority for sustainable economic growth and future knowledge economy and it's only possible when we have such a research scholar who has the capacity to plan, monitor, reflect and evaluate the environment. The study recommends that higher education policy makers focus on the required skills and their utility and keep focus to minimize the stressors and evaluate this territory population so that their prestige, social participation, self-efficacy and morale may be highly protected for their wellbeing and future success. The study provides guidelines for supervisors to get insight and find out genuine stressors and finding ways and suggestions for coping strategies as the issue that may damage their work potential and affect their well-being. Uneasiness spoils an individual mentally, cognitively and academically and pushes him back into a permanent state of stagnation and in some cases force to quit the degree. The study intends to prove that emotional intelligence gives a pathway to manage, comprehend, and use their relevant emotional traits and cognitive ability to go through challenging research journeys. The study put its focus on the well-being of university students that affect their autonomy, academic outcomes and overall purpose in life and eventually to lead better. The study guide teachers /research supervisors and organizations to focus on stressors of research students by best utilizing the self-regulation and emotional intelligence for practicing meta-cognitive and interpersonal skills. Doctoral study or research degree is considered the game of nerves. This phase of academic life left some memorable events and

learning trends that affect the individual in a very long run and even become part of his lifelong learning. This is evident from the opinions of research supervisors when they share the experience of their supervisors their own memories of that phase become alive as they are experiencing the same phase just now. Moreover, few teachers adopt those strategies to their students which were applied at their time over them. Effective leadership with well-defined objectives, faculty training and support programs, and acknowledgment of research output, encouragement of faculty collaboration, and balanced teaching and research responsibilities are all necessary for establishing a supportive research culture. Therefore, supervisors, supervisees, and institutions working together will help students achieve their ultimate aim of finishing their research successfully. In order to produce high-quality research results, this document provides a thorough guidance to pertinent authorities. Self-regulated learning is a skill, ability, and behavior as well as one of the 21st-century skills crucially needed in an academic context. It must be consciously nurtured, promoted, and utilized for better utility of cognitive, metacognitive, personal, and environmental learning (Khanm & Hassan, 2024) To address learning trends and skill development, this skill helps the learner be self-sufficient and supports him across the discipline and the workplace and situation. Emotional intelligence reflects the learner's potential and helps him manage his responsibilities adjustably. Emotionally intelligent learners are good at relationship management and running their life affairs smoothly. It consciously needs to be developed and promoted among students so that they can smoothly run their life tasks more comfortably (Khanm & Hassan, 2024)

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